

Sustainable Effect of Green House Gas Emissions from Indian Poultry Farms

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Abstract

A survey concentrates on Poultry greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Greenhouses work by allowing solar radiation into the house, but limiting the amount of radiation that can get back out. Greenhouse gasses work the same way on a global scale by changing the makeup of the atmosphere. They are defined by their radioactive forces (defined as the change in net irradiance at atmospheric boundaries between different layers of the atmosphere) which change the earth's atmospheric energy balance. These gasses can prevent heat from radiating or reflecting away from the earth and thus may result in atmospheric warming. The GHGs of particular concern in poultry production are; carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and methane (CH₄). The main objective of this paper effect of green house gas emission from Indian poultry sector poultry emission an briefly to make the farmers to aware reduction of global warming and green house gas emissions. Finally this paper focuses on how to reduce emission from poultry production systems.

Keywords: GHG, Emissions, Global warming, Poultry houses.

Introduction

Livestock accounts for about 18 % of the global GHGs emissions including CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation, N₂O emissions from manure and fertilizer, and CO₂ emissions from land-use change and agricultural energy use (FAO 2006). Livestock constitutes a major anthropogenic source of methane emission from agriculture sector. The methane emissions from livestock have two components: emissions from 'enteric fermentation' and 'manure management'. About 37 % of anthropogenic methane is attributed to enteric fermentation by ruminants as part of their normal digestive processes. Livestock manure management is also a significant source of methane with global emissions accounting to 9.3 Tg/year (Scheehle and Kruger 2006). Livestock also contributes a small but significant emission of nitrous oxide (N₂O) from animal waste management systems. Abha Chhabra (2012)

Greenhouse gases have far-ranging environmental and health effects. They cause climate change by trapping heat, and they also contribute to respiratory disease from smog and air pollution. Extreme weather, food supply disruptions, and increased wildfires are other effects of climate change caused by greenhouse gases. In the recent period, the atmospheric increase in greenhouse gases (GHGs) resulting mainly due to anthropogenic activities has become a cause of serious concern due to their impact on the earth's radiation budget and related global environmental change issues. The understanding and quantifying the non-CO₂

GHGs emissions is important because each gas is more effective, molecule-for-molecule at trapping heat than CO₂ (IPCC 2001). As a result, their emission contributes significantly to climate change. Furthermore, including non-CO₂ GHGs in an abatement strategy can be less expensive and more effective in mitigating climate change (Hansen et al. 2000). Methane (CH₄) is the second most important GHG after carbon dioxide (CO₂), and contributes ~15 % to the global warming (IPCC 2001). Methane remains in the atmosphere for ~9–15 years and is about 21 times more effective in trapping heat in the atmosphere than CO₂ over a 100-year period (FAO 2006). The global atmospheric concentration of methane has increased from a pre-industrial value of ~715 ppb (1 ppb010–9) to 1,732 ppb in the early 1990s, to 1,774 ppb in 2005. It is very likely that the observed increase in methane concentration is due to human-related activities, predominantly agriculture and fossil fuel use (IPCC 2007).

Review of literature

Sylvia H. Vetter (2017) identify agriculture is a major source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions globally. The growing global population is putting pressure on agricultural production systems that aim to secure food production while minimizing GHG emissions. In this study, the GHG emissions associated with the production of major food commodities in India are calculated using the Cool Farm Tool. GHG emissions, based on farm management for major crops (including cereals like wheat and

rice, pulses, potatoes, fruits and vegetables) and livestock-based products (milk, eggs, chicken and mutton meat), are quantified and compared. Livestock and rice production were found to be the main sources of GHG emissions in Indian agriculture with a country average of 5.65 kg CO₂eq kg⁻¹ rice, 45.54 kg CO₂eq kg⁻¹ mutton meat and 2.4 kg CO₂eq kg⁻¹ milk. Production of cereals (except rice), fruits and vegetables in India emits comparatively less GHGs. **Khondokar Mizanur Rahman (2011)** this research is to determine the anaerobic digestion (AD) potential and green house gas mitigation of small and medium anaerobic digester systems in Bangladesh which could provide energy for the country's need. This was determined for two common feedstocks: cattle dung and poultry litter. A third potential feedstock is also investigated as a novel and significant new source: waste rice straw used in cattle markets. These three feedstocks were chosen because between them, they cover a large fraction of scenarios in the country where AD could be used. All of the data needed to determine the energy parameters of these three representative AD facility types were collected (i.e. biogas yield, biogas composition, life cycle data). Highest biogas yield of 0.099 m³ /kg feedstock and methane percentage 74.4% were found from cattle market rice straw feedstock. The relative potential contributions to energy were then calculated. **Atul Kumar (2020)** to analysis during the recent past, poultry sector has shown immense adaptations to meet the ever-increasing demand for safe meat and eggs. However, this growth has been accompanied by structural changes within the industry which has led to emergence of various environmental and public health concerns ranging from water, air and soil pollution to ecological imbalances, biodiversity losses and occupational health and safety hazards. This paper analyses the environmental and human health impacts of intensive poultry production and various technical strategies to mitigate these issues. **Abha Chhabra (2013)** examine the study presents a detailed inventory of GHG emissions at district/state level from different age-groups, indigenous and exotic breed of different Indian livestock categories estimated using the recent census 2003 and countryspecific emission coefficients based on IPCC guidelines. The

total methane emission including enteric fermentation and manure management of livestock was estimated at 11.75 Tg/year for the year 2003. Enteric fermentation constitutes ~91 % of the total methane emissions from Indian livestock. Dairy buffalo and indigenous dairy cattle together contribute 60 % of the methane emissions. The total nitrous oxide emission from Indian livestock for the year 2003 is estimated at 1.42 Gg/year, with 86.1 % contribution from poultry. The total GHGs emission from Indian livestock is estimated at 247.2 Mt in terms of CO₂ equivalent emissions **NathanFiala (2007)** this paper estimates future meat consumption and discusses the potential aggregate environmental impact of this production if the use of CAFOs is expanded. I first separate meat into beef, chicken and pig products and estimate the elasticity's associated with each product in order to forecast the world demand for meat. Using research on the environmental impact of food production in the US, which uses one of the most efficient CAFO processes in the world, I then calculate the total potential greenhouse emissions of this meat production and discuss the impact of these consumption patterns. To find that, under an expanded CAFO system, meat production in the future will still be a large producer of greenhouse gases, accounting for up to 6.3% of current greenhouse gas emissions in 2030. **Sheikh Firdous Ahmad (2022)** in their research work concentrate one of the exciting developments that can significantly reduce GHG emissions is microbial modulation. Several approaches ranging from dietary manipulation to sophisticated genetic biotechnological techniques have been attempted to manipulate the microbial environment, to reduce GHG emissions, mainly methane. Sustainable practices to mitigate methane in ruminants are felt to be the most necessary without affecting production. To minimize GHG emission, ionospheres, organic acids, and oils are part of food manipulation. In his work to address GHG emissions, mainly methane, from agriculture and allied industries, and possible mitigation measures to facilitate sustainable production with minimal environmental impact.

Consequences Of the Greenhouse Effect

Thawing of glacial masses.

Flooding of islands and coastal cities.

Hurricanes will be more devastating.

Migration of species.

Desertification of fertile areas.

Impact on agriculture and livestock.

The main driver of climate change is the greenhouse effect. Some gases in the Earth's atmosphere act a bit like the glass in a greenhouse, trapping the sun's heat and stopping it from leaking back into space and causing global warming. The greenhouse effect is the way in which heat is trapped close to Earth's surface by "greenhouse gases." These heat-trapping gases can be thought of as a blanket wrapped around Earth, keeping the planet toastier than it would be without them. An increase in the atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gases produces a positive climate forcing, or warming effect. From 1990 to 2019, the total warming effect from greenhouse gases added by humans to the Earth's atmosphere increased by 45 percent. Greenhouse gases keep our planet livable by holding onto some of Earth's heat energy so that it doesn't all escape into space. This heat trapping is known as the greenhouse effect. Just as too little greenhouse gas makes Earth too cold, too much greenhouse gas makes Earth too warm.

Mitigating GHG Emissions

Mitigation, in relation to climate change, is any practice that reduces the net amount of GHGs released into the atmosphere. Mitigation strategies in animal agriculture are generally divided into four main categories

- production efficiency
- manure management
- energy efficiency
- carbon sequestration

Improving production efficiency will increase output of meat, milk, and eggs per unit of input, thereby reducing GHG emissions per unit of product produced (Smith, 2014b). Proper manure management will reduce GHG emissions and has the added benefit of protecting air and water quality. Installing energy efficient lighting such as LED lamps, along with efficient heating and cooling systems, will lessen GHG emissions and reduce energy bills. Carbon sequestration increases organic matter in soils. However, because of the wide diversity in livestock and poultry production systems and differences in farm operation

management practices, identifying effective mitigation strategies is often challenging.

For example, Dunkley (2011) reported that about 65 percent of GHG emissions from broiler and pullet farms were from propane use (used for brooding young birds during colder periods of the year), while only 0.3 percent of emissions from breeder farms were from propane use. However, on breeder farms, Dunkley (2011) indicated that about 85 percent of GHG emissions were the result of electricity used for lighting and ventilation, while pullet and broiler farms had 30 and 29 percent emissions, respectively, from electricity use.

Every farming operation is different and poultry growers must determine where the largest gains in efficiency can be realized on their operation. Many poultry houses have been upgraded to varying degrees in recent years to improve their production and energy efficiency. However, there are still numerous houses with room for improvement in the areas of propane and electricity use and manure management.

Poultry House Emissions

Human activities, including modern agriculture, contribute to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Greenhouses work by allowing solar radiation into the house, but limiting the amount of radiation that can get back out. Greenhouse gasses work the same way on a global scale by changing the makeup of the atmosphere. They are defined by their radioactive forces (defined as the change in net irradiance at atmospheric boundaries between different layers of thermosphere) which change the earth's atmospheric energy balance. These gases can prevent heat from radiating or reflecting away from the earth and thus may result in atmospheric warming. The GHGs of particular concern in poultry production are; carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and methane (CH₄).

Carbon Dioxide, Nitrous Oxide and Methane: Their Relationship with the Poultry Industry

Much of the carbon dioxide equivalent that the poultry industry generates is primarily from the utilization of fossil fuels in the form of purchased electricity, propane use in stationary combustion units such as furnaces or incinerators, and diesel use in mobile combustion units such as trucks, tractors and generators that are used on the

farm. In the animal industry, the consumption of plants (feed) by animals eventually results in the division of the carbon into either animal biomass (meat and eggs) or carbon dioxide respired by animals and fecal deposition of carbon in unutilized co-products (manure). Aside from the fossil fuel emissions on poultry farms, nitrous oxide and methane gases are also emitted from manure during handling and storage. Nitrous oxide and methane emissions depend on management decisions about manure disposal and storage, as these gases are formed in decomposing manures as a by-product of nitrification de-nitrification and methanol genesis, respectively. Stored manure will only emit nitrous oxide if nitrification occurs, which is likely to take place provided there is an adequate oxygen supply. Indirect GHG emissions of ammonia and other nitrogen compounds also occur from manure management systems and soils (Dr. Rajesh Singh) 2020.

Objective

Effect of green house gas emission from Indian poultry sector poultry
 How to reduce emission from poultry production systems.

Methodology

In this study carried out only for secondary data sources the methodological approach used for estimation of livestock based methane emissions from enteric fermentation and manure management at

the district level respectively, has been discussed in detail in Chhabra et al. (2009).

How does poultry farming contribute to global warming?

Several factors affect methane and nitrous oxide emissions from manure, including temperature, moisture content, and oxygen. Methane production from animal manure increases with increased temperature. This is where the majority of the methane is emitted during poultry production.(30-Mar-2011). This new report from the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) presents the results from an assessment carried out to improve the understanding of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions along livestock supply chains for pigs, poultry meat and eggs.(Jackie Linden 2013). As per the FAO report the livestock sector is one of the fastest growing sub-sectors of the agricultural economy, and faces several unprecedented and concomitant challenges, according to the FAO report, Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Pig and Chicken Supply Chain. The sector needs to respond to the increasing demands for livestock products that are arising from population growth and changing consumer preferences. It also has to adapt to changes in the economic and policy contexts, and in the natural environment upon which production depends. At the same time, it has to improve its environmental performance and mitigate its impact on climate.

Graph: 1-Methane Emissions from Indian Livestock

Source: Long-

term changes in Indian livestock population during 1951–2003

Major Long-Lived Greenhouse Gases and Their Characteristics

In animal agriculture, the greatest contribution to methane emissions is enteric

fermentation (23 percent) and manure management (9 percent). Enteric fermentation is the most important source of methane in dairy production, while most of the methane from poultry and swine production originates from manure. When comparing the distribution of methane emissions from enteric fermentation among

animal types (Figure 4), poultry had the lowest amount with 0.57 pounds of methane per animal per year when compared to dairy cattle, which produces 185 to 271 pounds of methane per animal per year, and swine, which produce 10.5 pounds of methane per animal per year (Monteny, Groenestein, & Hilhorst, 2001).

Graph: 2- Methane Emissions

Source : Monteny, Groenestein, & Hilhorst, 2001

Table: 1- Green house gas process and warming potential

Green House Gas	How It's Produced	Average Lifetime In The Atmosphere	100-Year Warming Potential	Global
Carbon dioxide	Emitted primarily through the burning of fossil fuel (oil, natural gas, and coal), solid waste, and tress and wood products. Changes in land use also play a role. Deforestation and soil degradation and Carbone dioxide to the atmosphere, while forest ragout takes it out of the atmosphere.	See below	1	
Methane	Emitted during the production and transport of oil and natural gas as well as coal. Methane emission also results from livestock and agricultural practices and from the anaerobic	109 years	27.0-29.8	

	decay of organic waste in municipal solid waste land files.		
Nitrous oxide	A group of gases that contain fluorine, including hydro fluorocarbons, per fluorocarbons, and sulfur hexafluoride, among other chemicals. These gases are emitted from a variety of industrial processes and commercial and household uses and do not occur naturally. Sometimes used as substitutes for ozone-depleting substances such as chlorofluorocarbons.	A few weeks to thousands of years	Varies (the highest is sulfur hexafluoride at 25,200)

Source: Monteny, Groenestein, & Hilhorst, 2001

India Has India Promised Emission Cuts

Prime Minister Narendra Modi has set his country a target of net zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2070, a significantly later deadline than many other countries. India has resisted setting overall reduction targets, saying industrialised nations should bear a much greater share of the burden as they have contributed far more towards global warming over time. It says an "emissions intensity" target, which measures emissions per unit of economic growth, is a fairer way to compare it with other countries, it says **By** (Shruti Menon 2021)

Carbon Intensity: GHG Emissions Relative to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) According to WRI CAIT data, India's GDP increased 357% from 1990 to 2014, while GHG emissions increased 180%. In 2014, India emitted more than twice the GHGs relative to GDP than the world average.²⁰ However, India has taken significant steps towards initiating a low carbon economy across various sectors,²¹ and pledged in its Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to reduce GDP emissions intensity by 33-35% by 2030 from 2005 levels.

Project to Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emission Launched

The project titled 'Circular Waste Solutions' in Tiruchi is focused on promoting carbon circular economy solutions in solid waste management with the support of Nationally Appropriate Mitigation Action

(NAMA) facility. The main objective of the project is to reduce Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions from waste by creating awareness of source segregation of waste and ensuring resource recovery from waste through decentralised processing of waste.

(Mayor M. Anbazhagan,) who launched the project at a function held here recently, said the Corporation had been taking a number of steps to decentralise domestic waste management. The new project would enable the civic body to fine-tune the exercise of segregating waste at source. India pledged to reduce the emission intensity of their economy by 33-35% compared to 2005 by the year 2030. In 2015, the country's GHG emissions stood at 3,571 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent (MtCO₂e) according to the data compiled by Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research. Interestingly enough, India's per capita emissions are less staggering with measurements identifying those levels to be 2.7tCO₂e in 2015. As a country, however, they are trending quite poorly. According to the IEA, in 2018 India's emission level was 2307.78 MtCO₂e, an increase of 335.33% from 1990.

India's Co₂ Emissions

Carbon dioxide emissions stem from burning fossil fuels and manufacturing cement. They include carbon dioxide produced during consumption of solid, liquid, and gas fuels and gas flaring. India has also been taking tangible steps to keep its Paris

Climate Agreement commitment intact, specifically by keeping CO2 emissions low and mitigating intensity. In 2019, CO2 emissions for India were 2,597.4 million tonnes. Over the last 50 years, emissions rose substantially from 232.8 to 2,597.4 million tonnes with an annual increase rate that reached a maximum of 11.65% in 2009 but eventually decreased to 1.6% in 2019. The chart below displays historical data sets from 2008 (as a baseline) through 2019 across aggregate, per capita, and intensity indices. The value in the data set is in Mt CO2.

How Can We Reduce Farming Emissions?

Improving forage quality and feeding a focus on improving forage quality, by picking

the right grass varieties and through timely operations when silage-making, can encourage intake, boosting yields and reducing the amount of bought-in feed required.

1. Keep Efficient Breeds
2. Try Mixing Chicken Feed With Whole Grains
3. Ferment Chicken Feed
4. Raise Active Foragers
5. Feed Them With Table Scrapes
6. Grow Your Own Feed
7. Let Your Birds Free-Range
8. Don't Overfeed Your Flock

Table: 2 - India Has Seen Greenhouse Gas Emissions

Climate	Value	Change %
2019	0.28	-3.26 percent
2018	0.29	-0.67 percent
2017	0.29	-2.41 percent
2016	0.30	-6.46 percent
2015	0.32	-5.04 percent
2014	0.34	0.63 percent
2013	0.34	-2.82 percent
2012	0.35	2.08 percent
2011	0.34	0.26 percent
2010	0.34	-2.99 percent
2009	0.35	3.52 percent
2008	0.34	Baseline

Source Public Knoema Data Hub

Emission projections for India are 9-12% lower in 2030 compared to previous projections in 2019 due to COVID-19's impact on the economy. Given that India has a GDP intensity target, its estimate of the emissions level for the NDC target is 8-11% lower compared to our previous projections in December 2019. India is on track to surpass its 2030 targets by a wide margin despite their ambitious target of 40% non-fossil fuel capacity share. Under current energy targets and policies, emissions are projected to increase by 24-25% above 2019 levels in 2030 because of the country's continued commitment to the coal industry. Such an increase of emissions is not consistent with the Paris Agreement. Instead, domestic emissions need to peak and start reducing, with international support.

India's existing target under the Paris Agreement "2°C-compatible" is still within the accepted range even though it allows the

country's total emissions to increase. According to Climate Scorecard projections, India could become a global climate leader with a "1.5°C compatible" rating if they enhance their NDC target, abandon plans to build new coal fired power plants, and phase out coal for power generation before 2040.

Conclusion

From all indications, the majority of GHG emissions generated from the poultry industry occur during the production stage (i.e. the grow-out, pullet, and breeder farms) and specifically come from propane and electricity use. It is therefore important that the poultry industry continues to work on improving efficiency when using fossil fuels in an effort to reduce GHG emissions. Engineering approaches will be necessary to address heating strategies and electricity use in the poultry houses. Agricultural engineers and poultry scientists are constantly working on ways to make these houses more efficient.

Other ways of becoming more efficient are through improving growth rate and feed efficiency. This has already been greatly improved in the poultry industry through genetic selection and improved nutrition.

When compared to other animal production systems, the modern broiler, layer, and turkey are considered to be very efficient. However, the scale of the U.S. poultry sector is vast and even small impacts can add up; therefore, we must be vigilant and continue working to reduce emissions and make the industry more sustainable. The estimated GHG emissions are essential inputs for generating spatially integrated multi-source GHG inventory at the national level and also as inputs to regional/global climate change models. The projected emissions provide important indicators for studying the future impacts of livestock to climate change and formulating policy measures for sustainable livestock production.

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